

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 27 May – 5 June 2023

Report published: May 2024

**Scandinavian brown bears:
Winter den sites and feeding ecology
of bears in the woodlands of Dalarna
county, Sweden**

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**Authors:
Andrea Friebe
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Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project**

**Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions**

Abstract

From 27 May to 4 June 2023, eight citizen scientists collected data on bear denning behaviour and feeding ecology by investigating the 2022/2023 hibernation season den sites of GPS-collared brown bears and by collecting fresh scats from day bed sites. 2023 was the third year of Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists assisting the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (SBBRP) after 2019 (followed by an enforced COVID-19-related break in 2020 and 2021) and 2022. It was the first year when field sampling was extended by two days to a total expedition length of ten days.

All field work was performed in the northern boreal forest zone in Dalarna and Gävleborg counties, south-central Sweden, which is the southern study area of the SBBRP. After two days of training, citizen scientists were divided into three to four sub-teams each day for seven days of field work. On field work days, citizen scientists were given locations where collar data suggested that bears had spent significant time either denning or around a kill site. Citizen scientists then went to those locations and defined den types (anthill den, soil den, rock den, basket den or uprooted tree den), recorded bed material thickness, size and content, as well as all tracks and signs around the den sites to elucidate whether a female had given birth to cubs during hibernation. All first scats after hibernation and hair samples found at those locations were also collected, and the habitat type around the den and the visibility of the den site were described.

In a very significant contribution to the SBBRP's field work, the expedition visited 43 winter positions and investigated 37 dens of 30 bears, which represents about 75% of all winter positions that the SBBRP recorded in 2022. Previous expeditions investigated 34% (2019) and 50% (2022) of all winter positions recorded. The significant 2023 expedition increase is due to the extra two field days introduced with this expedition. Additionally, the expedition collected 100% of scat samples that the SBBRP normally collects during a research season. Previous expeditions collected 50% (2019) and 100% (2022).

As in 2022, two bears shifted their dens at least once during the hibernation season. In total, the expedition found 37 dens; five soil dens, eleven anthill dens, four anthill/soil dens, seven stone/rock den, five dens under uprooted trees and five basket dens. Unusually again, as in 2022, one pregnant female that gave birth to three cubs during winter, and one female that hibernated together with dependent offspring spent the winter in basket dens. Normally basket dens are mainly used by large males.

Excavated bear dens had an average outer length of 2.0 m, an outer width of 2.2 m, and an outer height of 0.7 m. The entrance on average comprised 16% of the open area. The inner length of the den was on average 1.4 m and the inner width was 1.3 m. The inner height of the dens was on average 0.7 m. Bears that hibernated in covered dens used mainly mosses (43%), field layer shrubs (21%) and branches (22%) as nest material, which reflected the composition of the field layer and ground layer that was present at the den site. However, bears that hibernated in open dens such as basket dens, preferred mosses (64%) followed by grass (17%); and field shrubs (17%) as nest material. The expedition found ten first post-hibernation bear scats at the den sites.

Twenty-seven bears selected their den sites in older forests, and three bears in younger forests. The habitat around the dens was dominated by spruce (*Picea abies*) 39%, scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) 36% and birch (*Betula pendula*, *Betula pubescens*) 26%.

The SBBRP is very thankful for Biosphere Expeditions' significant annual data collection aiding its long-term study of brown bears. With the help of these data, three reports and publications are on course to be published within the next two years: (1) A global review of the factors influencing den types of brown bears, (2) a brown bear dietary specialisation Master thesis based on faecal samples and (3) a publication on the effect of den type on hibernation duration and reproductive success.

Sammandrag

Från den 27 maj till den 4 juni 2023 åtta expeditionsdeltagare samlade in data om björnens vinterbeteende och födointag genom att undersöka idesplatserna där björnar har legat i vintersömnen under säsongen 2022-2023 och de samlade samla färsk spillning från daglegor från GPS-märkta brunbjörnar. 2023 var det tredje året som Biosphere Expeditions expeditionsdeltagare bistod det Skandinaviska Brunbjörnsforskningsprojektet (SBBRP) efter 2019 (följt av ett tvångspaus relaterat till COVID-19 år 2020 och 2021) och 2022. Det var det första året då fältprovtagningen förlängdes med två dagar till en total expeditionsperiod på tio dagar.

Allt fältarbete utfördes i den norra boreala skogszonen i Dalarnas och Gävleborgs län, södra Sverige, vilket är det södra studieområdet för SBBRP. Efter två dagars utbildning inom fältarbete delades expeditionsdeltagarna in i tre till fyra grupper. Alla studiepositioner tillhandahölls av expeditionsforskaren och endast data och prover från radiomärkta björnar med en VHF- eller GPS-sändare samlades in. Expeditionsdeltagarna gick sedan till dessa platser och definierade idestyp (myrstackide, jordide, stenide, korgide eller ide under en rotvälta), registrerade tjocklek, storlek och innehåll av bäddmaterial samt alla spår och tecken runt idesplatserna för att dokumentera om en hona hade fött ungar under vintersömnen. Alla första spillningar efter vintersömnen samlades in, och habitatet runt idesplatsen karterades.

I ett mycket betydande bidrag till SBBRPs fältarbete besökte expeditionen 43 vinterpositioner och undersökte 37 bon av 30 björnar, vilket representerar cirka 75% av alla vinterpositioner som SBBRP registrerade år 2022. Tidigare expeditioner undersökte 34% (2019) och 50% (2022) av alla registrerade vinterpositioner. Den betydande ökningen av expeditionen 2023 beror på de extra två fältdagarna som infördes med denna expedition. Dessutom samlade expeditionen in 100% av avföringsproverna som SBBRP normalt samlar in under en forskningssäsong. Tidigare expeditioner samlade in 50% (2019) och 100% (2022).

Som 2022 hade två björnar flyttat från sina iden minst en gång under vintersäsongen. Totalt hittade expeditionen 37 iden; fem jordiden, elva myrstackiden, fyra myrstack-/jordide, sju stenide, fem ide under rotvälta och fem korgiden. Ovanligt igen, som 2022, hade en dräktig hona som födde tre ungar under vintern, samt en hona som övervintrade tillsammans med beroende avkomma, tillbringat vintern i korgiden. Vanligtvis används koriden främst av stora hanar.

Utgrävda björnide hade en genomsnittlig yttre längd på 2,0 m, en yttre bredd på 2,2 m och en yttre höjd på 0,7 m. Ingången utgjorde i genomsnitt 16% av den öppna ytan. Den inre längden på idet var i genomsnitt 1,4 m och den inre bredden var 1,3 m. Den inre höjden på bon var i genomsnitt 0,7 m. Björnar som övervintrade i utgrävda iden använde främst mossor (43%), bärris (21%) och grenar (22%) som bäddmaterial, vilket speglade sammansättningen av fältskiktet och markskiktet som fanns på idesplatsen. Björnar som övervintrade i öppna iden som korgiden föredrog mossor (64%) följt av gräs (17%); och bärris (17%)

Tjugosju björnar valde sina idesplatser i äldre skogar, och tre björnar i yngre skogar. Habitatet runt iden dominerades av gran (*Picea abies*) 39%, tall (*Pinus sylvestris*) 36% och björk (*Betula pendula*, *Betula pubescens*) 26%.

Den SBBRP är mycket tacksamt för Biosphere Expeditions betydande årliga datainsamling som hjälper till i deras långsiktiga studie av brunbjörnar. Med hjälp av dessa data är tre rapporter och publikationer på väg att publiceras inom de närmaste två åren: (1) En global översikt över faktorer som påverkar idestyperna hos brunbjörnar, (2) en masteruppsats om brunbjörnens födoval baserad på avföringsprover och (3) en publikation om effekten av idestyp på övervintringens längd och reproduktiv framgång.

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1. Expedition review

M. Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per Friebe & Hammer (2020). The expedition has now for three years (2019, 2022, 2023, with an enforced COVID-19-related hiatus in 2020 and 2021) assisted a long-term research project in Dalarna county in Sweden to help study and protect the local brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) population.

Details about the history, distribution and population dynamics of brown bears in Sweden and Norway, the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project, bear biology, detailed background to den site surveys as well as scat inventory surveys can be found in chapter 2.1. of Friebe & Hammer (2023).

1.2. Dates & team

The expedition ran over a 10-day period and comprised a team of national and international citizen scientists, professional scientists and an expedition leader. Group dates were as shown in the team list below. Dates were chosen so that the expedition could visit the bear dens early in the season when tracks and signs were still fresh (bears usually leave their den sites from mid-April until the end of May).

The expedition scientist and co-author of this report was Dr. Andrea Friebe, the expedition leader was Roland Arnison. The expedition team of citizen scientists was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

27 May – 5 June 2023: Michael Casey (USA), Stephen Crowther (UK), Edward Durell (Germany), Kristin Haase* (Germany), Torsten John (Germany), Petra Löbel (Germany), Penny Smith (Australia), John Smith (Australia), Louise Webb (assistant & chef).

*blogger: See [coverage](#) (in German) and [video](#).

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place. There were no medical incidences during the expedition.

1.3. Partners

Biosphere Expeditions' main partner on this expedition is [Björn & Vildmark](#) (Bears & Wilderness in Swedish), a company responsible for science communication, information and guided tours in the [Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project](#). Björn & Vildmark was established in 2001 with the purpose of distributing information about bear research and bear behaviour to the local population and managers. Dr. Andrea Friebe of Björn & Vildmark is also a researcher in the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project and the expedition followed the project's methodologies and shared its data with it.

1.4. Acknowledgements

This study was conducted by Biosphere Expeditions which runs wildlife conservation expeditions all over the globe. Without our expedition team members (listed above) who provided an expedition contribution and gave up their spare time to work as research assistants, none of this research would have been possible. The support team and staff (also mentioned above) were central to making it all work on the ground. Thank you to all of you and the ones we have not managed to mention by name (you know who you are) for making it all happen. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions for their sponsorship and/or in-kind support.

The expedition was embedded within the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project and we would like to thank the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA), the Norwegian Environment Directorate, the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency and the Swedish Association for Hunting and Wildlife Management for funding.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:
<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Expedition diary/blog:
<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/sweden-2023/>

Expedition details, background, pictures, videos, etc.
<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/sweden>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid towards expedition costs a contribution of €2,580 per person per 10-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special non-personal equipment, and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	18,174
 Expenditure	
Base camp and food includes all board & lodging, base camp services	4,184
Vehicles and fuel includes fuel, wear & tear, car hire charges; also includes per km support payment from Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project	1,263
Equipment and hardware includes research materials & gear, etc.	261
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff & expenses	4,886
Administration includes registration fees, sundries, etc.	26
Team recruitment Sweden as estimated % of PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	7,334
 Income – Expenditure	 220
 Total percentage spent directly on project	 99%

2. Winter den sites and scat sampling of Scandinavian brown bears in Sweden

Andrea Friebe
Björn & Vildmark
Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project

2.1. Introduction

Details about the history, distribution and population dynamics of brown bears in Sweden and Norway, the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project, bear biology, detailed background to den site surveys as well as scat inventory surveys can be found in chapter 2.1. of Friebe & Hammer (2023) and in the field protocols of Appendix II and III.

Figure 2.1a. Development of the brown bear population in Sweden. Estimated numbers of bears in different years, data from www.naturvardsverket.se.

Figure 2.1b. Map showing estimated bear population density in 2022 in Sweden.

The darker the colour, the higher the density. (Sköld, M. and Åsbrink, J. 2023).

Red rectangle = southern study site of the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project = expedition study site.

In summary, the expedition assists the pan-Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (SBBRP) with labour-intensive data gathering, which is well suited to citizen science involvement. In particular, the expedition concentrates on

- investigating den sites where radio marked bears of the SBBRP have hibernated the previous winter
- finding and collecting scats at those den sites, as well as cluster sites (places where GPS collars show that bears have spent prolonged periods of time, often a feeding or kill site).

These research activities lend themselves to citizen science data gathering and the data gleaned are a significant help to the SBBRP and its aims to elucidate denning behaviour and for future analysis about bear feeding ecology. This is important, because human disturbance often has a negative effect on bears such as den abandonment, stress, habitat loss or fragmentation of habitat, including alterations in food availability, and reduced reproductive success. Information about den site selections and the bears' choice of food will be helpful for managers when making decisions for brown bear conservation. Climate change is also another important factor, which can alter food availability and type, and therefore this denning duration. The emerging causal chain seems to be shorter, less severe winters and through this better food availability, which results in reduced denning duration.

2.2. Materials and methods

Study area and population

This study was conducted in the northern boreal forest zone in Dalarna and Gävleborg counties, south-central Sweden (~61°N, 15°E), which is the southern study area of the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project. The area comprises about 13,000 km², is hilly, and is covered with coniferous forests with interspersed lakes and bogs. Altitudes range from 200 m in the southeast to 1,000 m in the west but are mostly (>90 %) below the treeline, which is at about 750 m (Dahle and Swenson 2003). The forest is dominated by Norway spruce (*Picea abies*), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), and birches (*Betula pendula* and *Betula pubescens*). Ground vegetation includes a variety of species of mosses, lichens, grass, heather and berries. Bilberries (*Vaccinium myrtillus*) and crowberries (*Empetrum nigrum* subsp. *hermaphroditum*) are the main autumn food resource of brown bears in this area (Opseth 1998).

The landscape is intersected by a dense network of logging tracks (0.7 km/km²) and a few high-traffic asphalted roads (0.14 km/km²) (Martin et al. 2010). The human population density is low and only a few small villages exist in the study area (Swenson et al. 1999).

Snow cover lasts from the end of October until late April and mean daily temperatures range from -7 °C in January to 15 °C in July (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute).

The study area of the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (Fig. 2.1b) is part of the southernmost core reproductive area for Scandinavian brown bears, with a population density of about 30 individuals per 1000 km² (Bellemain et al. 2005, Solberg et al. 2006, Kindberg et al. 2011). The brown bear is a game species and legal hunting is the single-most important cause of mortality for brown bears in Sweden (Bischof et al. 2009).

The annual brown bear hunt runs from 21 August until quotas are reached (45–75 bears are harvested per year in the study area), but stops by no later than 15 October, in order to protect hibernating bears from disturbance.

Training and deployment of citizen scientists

The expedition team comprised eight citizen scientists recruited by Biosphere Expeditions, one expedition leader and one assistant/chef from Biosphere Expeditions and the expedition scientist (and lead author of this report).

Training (two days) and field work with sampling (seven days) was conducted as per Friebe & Hammer (2023).

2.3. Results

Den sites

Eight citizen scientists and two staff investigated 43 winter positions of 30 different bears from 27 May to 5 June 2023 (Appendix I)

. All positions investigated were first recorded during the winter 2022/2023, except for five den positions, which bears used the previous 2021/2022 winter. Two bears shifted their dens at least once during the hibernation season. One female bear reused the den of the former winter season, which is very unusual for bears in Sweden. At 37 out of the 43 positions identified, the expedition found actual bear dens. Den positions are shown in Fig. 2.3a.

Den type

In total, the expedition investigated: 5 soil dens, 11 anthill dens, 4 anthill/soil dens, 7 stone/rock dens, 5 dens under uprooted trees and 5 basket dens. One pregnant female that gave birth to three cubs during winter, one female that hibernated together with dependent offspring, and three solitary bears spent the winter in basket dens. Normally basket dens are mainly used by large males. All dens were constructed inside, rather than at the periphery, of the home range. Rock dens were mainly used by solitary bears.

Den measurements

Excavated bear dens such as anthill and soil dens had an average outer length of 2.0 m (range 1.1 m - 3.1 m), outer width of 2.2 m (range 1.0 m - 3.5 m) and outer height of 0.7 m (range 0.1 m - 1.7 m). Den entrances were on average 0.6 m high (range 0.3 m - 0.9 m) and 0.7 m wide (range 0.3 m - 1.0 m). The entrance represented on average 16% of the open area. The inner length of the den was on average 1.4 m (range 0.7 m - 2.3 m) and the inner width was 1.3 m (range 0.6 m - 1.9 m). The inner height of the dens was on average 0.7 m (range 0.6 m - 1.0 m).

Bed material

Figure 2.3b. Bed material. Top: Available field and ground layer, which can be used as bed material in a radius of 10 m around covered and open winter dens of hibernating bears in Sweden. Bottom: Collected bed material that was found in left: covered winter dens (n=26), and right: open winter dens (n=11).

Bears often use field layer shrubs (from berry bushes or heather) or grass, but also ground layer material such as moss and lichens as bed material. Also branches from trees can be collected. Bears that constructed open dens hibernated in habitats where more grass (29% vs 5%), but less field shrubs (15% vs 39%) was available. However, the amount of grass in the collected bed material was the same for both covered and open dens. Moss has good insulating properties and was the main bedding material (64%) in open dens (Fig. 2.3.b).

Samples

The expedition found ten first post-hibernation bear scats at the den sites. We examined the scats, packed and labelled them and stored them in a -20°C freezer for further analysis. Signs of cubs (climbing marks, scats and small day beds) were found at eight den sites.

Habitat

None of the dens were located in water-rich areas such as bogs or swamps. Twenty-seven bears selected their den sites in older forests (type G1: medium tree > 10 cm diameter at breast height) and three bears hibernated in younger forest (type R2: medium tree > 1.3 m but < 10 cm in diameter at breast height (1.3 m)). Twelve dens were located on mountain sides or slopes, one den was located on a cliff edge (Fig. 2.3c) and 13 dens on level ground.

Figure 2.3c. Dens located on a cliff edge (left) and on a slope (right).

The habitat in a radius of 50 m around the den was dominated by spruce (*Picea abies* 39%), followed by Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* 36%), and birches (*Betula pendula* & *pubescens* 26%). At the den site on a smaller scale (10 m radius around the den), the tree species composition was similar. Birch trees represented 26%, spruce 35% and pine 39% of tree species. The sighting distance to the den was on average 19 m. In 85% of cases, it was the vegetation that limited the visibility to the den, in 15% the landscape terrain was the reason.

Scat sampling at cluster sites

The expedition group found 34 scats at cluster positions. At eight (24%) cluster sites the expedition group found remains of kills. Seven kill remains had been moose calves of a very young age, probably only a few weeks old, one kill was an adult moose. The calves were often buried in the ground close to the bear's day bed and some bears also covered the remains with berry shrubs.

Five of the eight kill remains were found at clusters from bears with dependent offspring. All scats were half dry or dry and had a solid, formed shape, except five scats that were moist and liquid.

2.4. Discussion

A detailed discussion of den type, abandonment and disturbance, as well as the effects of climate change on bears, their diet and denning behaviour is given in the discussions of Friebe and Hammer (2020 & 2023).

Here we concentrate on the results of the expeditions and how they add value to the larger Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (SBBRP), for which the lead author works full-time.

2023 was the third year of citizen scientists assisting the SBBRP after 2019 (followed by an enforced COVID-19-related break in 2020 and 2021) and 2022. It was the first year when field sampling was extended by two days to a total expedition length of ten days.

The expedition visited 43 winter positions and investigated 37 dens, which represents about 75% of all winter positions that the SBBRP recorded in 2022. Previous expeditions investigated 34% (2019) and 50% (2022) of all winter positions recorded (Fig 2.4a). The significant 2023 expedition increase is due to the extra two field days introduced with this expedition.

Additionally, the expedition collected 100% of scat samples that the SBBRP normally collects during a research season. Previous expeditions collected 50% (2019) and 100% (2022) (Fig 2.4a).

Figure 2.4a. Winter positions and scat samples results of the expeditions 2019, 2022 and 2023.

From these basic data points, it is easy to see that the expedition's citizen scientists made a very significant contribution to the SBBRP's field work and we thank all the participants and Biosphere Expeditions for their help and dedication.

Long-term research projects require data collection over many years, but they also offer several advantages. They enable a deeper understanding of processes and phenomena over an extended period, leading to more informed scientific insights. They also allow the identification of trends and patterns over time, providing insights into long-term changes. All in all this helps with understanding and detecting long-term impacts of events or changes, such as the influence of climate change or human activity on ecosystems. Analysing data over an extended period can also help identify potential risks and opportunities early, leading to more informed management and conservation decisions. Finally, long-term studies provide the opportunity to test and validate hypotheses over an extended period, resulting in more robust scientific findings.

The SBBRP is therefore very thankful that Biosphere Expeditions helps us gather information and data for these important long-term studies. Many data points have to be collected for many years before scientific conclusions can be drawn and this is one of the reasons why open-ended year-on-year support by Biosphere Expeditions is so useful, especially because many grants, by comparison, are for a few years only. The following reports and publications are on course to be published within the next two years:

1. A global review of the factors influencing den types of brown bears: Throughout their range, brown bears show a wide range of den types used for hibernation. The forthcoming publication will review the literature with data throughout bears' range to document the types of dens that are used, and investigate whether factors of geology, landform or the presence of large anthills influence these choices. For example, it seems that cave-denning bears are most common in karst areas. Denning data from Biosphere Expeditions / the SBBRP will be used to examine whether factors such as landform, geology, presence of permafrost, presence of large anthills by study area, etc. affect the den type used by brown bears. This will elucidate which den types brown bears prefer, when they have the choice.

2. Dietary specialisation in brown bears based on faecal samples (new Master thesis in 2025): Scat data collected by Biosphere Expeditions will flow into this thesis.

3. Effect of den type on hibernation duration and reproductive success: The factors influencing the large-scale hibernation site selection of brown bears in central Sweden are relatively well-known. However, there is a lack of knowledge regarding how den type affects reproductive success and hibernation duration. The objective of this study is to determine the factors that influence the den type used by brown bears and the effects of the den type on hibernation duration and reproductive success. Denning data from Biosphere Expeditions / the SBBRP will be used in this study.

Given all of the above, the 2024 expedition should continue to:

- investigate den sites of brown bears to document effects of climate change and human activity on brown bear den site selection
- collect bear scat in order to gain more knowledge about the seasonal differences in choice of food

- examine first scats of female brown bears after hibernation in more detail in order to gain more information about the virtually unknown areas of cub loss or foetus abortions during hibernation
- document signs of cubs at den sites to elucidate brown bear reproduction parameters, such as age of primiparity, cub survival and reproduction rates
- help the project to search for GPS collars that have fallen off bears in the woods
- help the project to find remains of dead bears to elucidate reasons of death such as illegal or intraspecific killing

In addition, the 2024 expedition should:

- help the project to test a new model of VHF-ear tags. Test the new VHF tags and compare their range with other VHF tags that have been used in the project.
- help to find four bears by radio telemetry (during the 2023 season, contact with four bears was lost due to battery malfunction of their GPS collars. The collars also have external VHF-transmitters on them, which can be used to locate the animals through manual triangulation).

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Appendix I: Details of bears and bear dens investigated by the expedition. The reproductive status shows if the bear hibernated alone (solitary), gave birth to cubs during hibernation in the den (pregnant), or hibernated together with dependent offspring (with offspring).

Hibernation season	ID #	Bearname	Den #	Sex	Born	Reproductive status	Den reused	Den type	Den used all winter
2021/2022	W1203	Pengel	1	F	2008	with offspring	yes	anthill	yes
2021/2022	W1509	Skärjämna	1	F	2014	pregnant	no	soil	yes
2021/2022	W1914	Vrala	1	F	adult	pregnant	no	anthill	yes
2021/2022	W2108	Gasloke	1	M	2014	solitary	no	uprooted tree	yes
2021/2022	W2113	Jordika	1	F	2017	pregnant	no	uprooted tree	yes
2022/2023	W0605	Sälga	1	F	2005	solitary	no	anthill	yes
2022/2023	W1203	Pengel	1	F	2008	pregnant	yes	anthill	yes
2022/2023	W1304	Bergsloga	1	F	2012	with offspring	no	uprooted tree	yes
2022/2023	W1418	Hässja	1	F	adult	solitary	no	basket	no
2022/2023	W1418	Hässja	2	F	adult	solitary	no	basket	no
2022/2023	W1505	Gymasa	1	F	adult	pregnant	no	anthill	unknown
2022/2023	W1509	Skärjämna	1	F	2014	with offspring	no	rock	no
2022/2023	W1702	Gädda	1	F	2016	with offspring	no	basket	yes
2022/2023	W1708	Letto	1	F	2016	pregnant	no	soil	yes
2022/2023	W1801	Storhamra	1	M	2015	solitary	no	anthill/soil	yes
2022/2023	W1803	Snyvla	1	F	2017	solitary	no	basket	no
2022/2023	W1813	Gutmyra	1	F	2017	solitary	no	anthill	unknown
2022/2023	W1815	Ottala	1	F	2017	pregnant	no	anthill	yes
2022/2023	W1914	Vråla	1	F	adult	with offspring	no	anthill/soil	yes
2022/2023	W2012	Lova	1	F	2019	solitary	no	soil	yes
2022/2023	W2014	Nyboda	1	F	2019	solitary	no	anthill	yes
2022/2023	W2016	Gangsa	1	F	2014	with offspring	no	soil	no
2022/2023	W2016	Gangsa	2	F	2014	with offspring	no	anthill/soil	no
2022/2023	W2019	Nissja	1	F	2016	pregnant	no	basket	yes
2022/2023	W2110	Musöra	1	F	2020	solitary	no	basket	no
2022/2023	W2110	Musöra	2	F	2020	solitary	no	anthill	no
2022/2023	W2110	Musöra	3	F	2020	solitary	no	anthill/soil	no
2022/2023	W2113	Jordika	1	F	2017	with offspring	no	anthill	yes
2022/2023	W2116	Näckila	1	F	2020	solitary	no	rock	yes
2022/2023	W2120	Klocka	1	F	2016	solitary	no	anthill	yes
2022/2023	W2204	Lommi	1	F	adult	pregnant	no	uprooted tree	yes
2022/2023	W2205	Flyta	1	F	adult	solitary	no	rock	yes
2022/2023	W2210	Kvista	1	F	2021	solitary	no	rock	yes
2022/2023	W2211	Hyla	1	F	2021	solitary	no	rock	no
2022/2023	W2212	Åsbo	1	M	adult	solitary	no	soil	yes
2022/2023	W2214	Turken	1	M	2021	solitary	no	uprooted tree	yes
2022/2023	W2215	Ticka	1	F	2021	solitary	no	rock	yes
2022/2023	W2216	Byxmyra	1	F	2021	solitary	no	rock	yes

Appendix II: Den mapping protocol

Skandinaviska Björnprojektet 2019		OBSERVER	PROTOCOL ID.:		YEAR (YYYY) MONTH (MM) DAY (DD)		
BEAR DEN							
RELATED TO							
LOCATION INFO AND YEAR DEN WAS USED	LOCAL NAME	COORDINATES (GPS) (N/E)		M. S. L.	DEN WAS USED WINTER <input type="checkbox"/> YEAR UNCERTAIN <input type="checkbox"/> YEAR EXACT <input type="checkbox"/>		
DEN WAS USED	<input type="checkbox"/> ALL OF WINTER	<input type="checkbox"/> PART OF WINTER FROM TO	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN	<input type="checkbox"/> DEN USED IN PREVIOUS YEAR (S) BY BEAR WITH ID-no.: YEAR(S) /			
POTENTIAL "DISTURBANCES" DURING USE OF DEN	<input type="checkbox"/> SKIING	<input type="checkbox"/> HUNTING	DISTURBANCE		COMMENT:		
	<input type="checkbox"/> CAPTURE	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN	<input type="checkbox"/> RECURRING	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN	BEAR LEFT DEN AFTER <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN		
	<input type="checkbox"/> SNOW MOBILE	<input type="checkbox"/> MILITARY	<input type="checkbox"/> TEMPORARY	DATE:			
	<input type="checkbox"/> FOREST FELLING	FROM TO					
	<input type="checkbox"/> OTHER (PROVIDE COMMENT)						
BEAR IDENTITY	DEN WAS USED BY: <input type="checkbox"/> UNMARKED BEAR <input type="checkbox"/> MARKED BEAR ID-NO.:			NAME:	SEX:		
DEN POSITION IN THE TERRAIN WITHIN A 50 M RADIUS AND INCLINE OF TERRAIN	<input type="checkbox"/> MOUNTAIN (ABOVE TREELINE) <input type="checkbox"/> DECIDUOUS FOREST <input type="checkbox"/> Evergreen FOREST <input type="checkbox"/> YOUNG FOREST (AVERAGE 3M) <input type="checkbox"/> CLEAR-CUT (LOWER THAN 1M) <input type="checkbox"/> MOUNTAIN SIDE <input type="checkbox"/> RAVINE <input type="checkbox"/> CLIFF EDGE <input type="checkbox"/> SLOPE <input type="checkbox"/> OTHER _____ <input type="checkbox"/> LEVEL GROUND <input type="checkbox"/> DEPRESSION <input type="checkbox"/> RIDGE BEARING (90 DEGREES): INCLINE (DEGREES):						
VEGETATION WITHIN 50M RADIUS IN PERCENT	TREES TALLER THAN 1M: (SUM OF ALL TREES EQUALS 100%, WRITE A ZERO FOR TREE SPECIES THAT ARE ABSENT) BIRCH: % SPRUCE: % PINE: % OTHER TREE SPP.: %, %, % (PROVIDE SPECIES NAME)						
NO. OF TREES TALLER THAN 3M WITHIN 10M RADIUS	(NB: NUMBER! NOT %, WRITE A ZERO FOR SPECIES WHERE NO TREES ARE PRESENT) BIRCH: SPRUCE: PINE: OTHER TREE SPP: (PROVIDE SPECIES NAME)						
HABITAT	TYPE:		Patch size: small medium large			TreeHT (m): P: S: D:	
	Densimeter		N	E	S	W	Stems/ha P: S: D:
	Concealment UR LW		N v t	E v t	S v t	W v t	Reliscope P: S: D:
GROUND VEG. & BARE GROUND/STONE WITHIN 10 M RADIUS, IN PERCENT	UNTOUCHED BARE GROUND AND BARE ROCK %		GROUND VEGETATION: %		AREA WHERE NOT POSSIBLE TO DETERMINE GROUND VEG COMPOSITION: % ADDS UP TO 100%		
GROUND VEGETATION WITHIN 10M RADIUS IN PERCENT (TOTAL GROUND + FIELD LAYER CAN EXCEED 100%)	TOTAL GROUND LAYER: %	MOSSES %	LICHENS % ADDS UP TO 100%				SIGNS: Beds _____ Scats _____ Anthills: _____ Treestumps: _____
	TOTAL FIELD LAYER: %	BERRY FOLIAGE %	HEATH. %	GRASSES %	OTHER (SPECIFY) %	OTHER (SPECIFY) % ADDS UP TO 100%	
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION	<input type="checkbox"/> YES Picture taken <input type="checkbox"/> YES Hair sample from the inside of the den taken						

TYPE OF DEN		<input type="checkbox"/> ANT HILL MIN. 80% ANT-HILL MATERIAL		<input type="checkbox"/> ROCK DEN		<input type="checkbox"/> NEST DEN		<input type="checkbox"/> UPROOTED TREE	
		<input type="checkbox"/> SOIL DEN MIN 80% SOIL DEN		<input type="checkbox"/> ANT HILL/SOIL DEN 20 - 80% ANT-HILL, REST SOIL MATERIALS		<input type="checkbox"/> OTHER _____			
DEN ENTRANCE & PROPORTION OPEN AREA IN PERCENT		BEARING: DEGREES (360°)		NO. OF OPENINGS (>5 CM) PCS		PROP. OPEN AREA INCL. ENTRANCE %		DEN COLLAPSED : <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> YES _____ <input type="checkbox"/> BEFORE <input type="checkbox"/> AFTER <input type="checkbox"/> DURING DENNING <input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN	
CEILING & WALL CONSIST OF		<input type="checkbox"/> SOIL		<input type="checkbox"/> ROCKS		<input type="checkbox"/> TREE ROOTS > 3 CM		<input type="checkbox"/> OTHER _____	
BED CONSISTS OF ADDS UP TO 100%		BERRY FOLIAGE %		MOSSES %		BRANCHES %		HEATHER %	
		LICHENS %		GRASSES %		OTHER %		OTHER %	
								BED REMOVED FROM DEN? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO	
DEN MEASUREMENTS									
1. OUTER LENGTH.....CM OBS: CM !!!									
2. OUTER WIDTH.....CM									
3. OUTER HEIGHT.....CM									
4. ENTRANCE HEIGHT*.....CM									
5. ENTRANCE WIDTH*.....CM									
6. ENTRANCE LENGTH**.....CM									
7. INNER ENTRANCE HEIGHT.....CM									
8. INNER ENTRANCE WIDTH**.....CM									
9. INNER LENGTH.....CM									
10. INNER WIDTH.....CM									
11. INNER HEIGHT.....CM									
12. BED LENGTH.....CM									
13. BED WIDTH.....CM									
14. BED DEPTH.....CM									
15. BED THICKNESS.....CM									
16. THICKNESS OF WALLS AND ROOF.....CM.....CM.....CM (6 MEASUREMENTS)CM.....CM.....CM									
*Maximum measurement for the bear, no cracks etc									
**when applicable									
SIGNS OF CUBS		<input type="checkbox"/> SCAT		<input type="checkbox"/> SCRATCHES		<input type="checkbox"/> OTHER _____			
USE DIGITAL CAMERA TO TAKE ONE PHOTO OF FRONT AND SIDE OF DEN, RESPECTIVELY AND ATTACH PRINT TO PROTOCOL. USE THIS SECTION TO DRAW A SCHEMATIC DRAWING OF THE DEN.									

Appendix III: Scat sampling protocol

Protocol - sample ID		Date (DDMMYY)	Time
Calendar week	Observer	Study	Bear Status
			Adult male <input type="checkbox"/>
			Lone female <input type="checkbox"/>
Bear ID	Name of bear	No. Cluster	Subad male <input type="checkbox"/>
			Subad female <input type="checkbox"/>
			Yearling female <input type="checkbox"/>
			Female/COY <input type="checkbox"/>
X Coord	Y Coord	No. beds	No. Scats
Bear LMT Start Date*	Bear LMT End Date*	Bear LMT Start time*	Bear LMT End time*
Scat condition	Scat shape**	Percent collected	Carcass***
Moist <input type="checkbox"/>	Solid <input type="checkbox"/>		Yes <input type="checkbox"/>
Half-dry <input type="checkbox"/>	Liquid <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>
Dry <input type="checkbox"/>			
Comments			

Scats can only be collected if they are within 5m from the bear bed.
If > 1 bed is available or if it unsure if the bear was alone, no scats should be collected.

*Note: these data are from the GIS

** If the shape of the original scat was solid ("sausage") shaped, or liquidish ("puddle")

*** If a carcass was present at the cluster where the scat was collected